

MODEL OF PASSIVE AND ACTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY DYNAMICS**Kostadinov O.***Ph.D., Guest Lecturer**Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy**Varna, Bulgaria**ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9183-5243***Abstract**

Learning a foreign language requires the perception and assimilation of foreign language knowledge to memorize and use it later. The process of remembering is accompanied by forgetting. Memorizing foreign words happens gradually and in stages, which is why foreign language vocabulary is divided into two categories: passive and active vocabulary. For these reasons, we have different degrees of mastery of foreign words. These features of the process of acquiring foreign language knowledge make it dynamic. Between passive and active vocabulary, there is constant movement of vocabulary in both directions. Repetition of foreign words from the passive vocabulary leads to their passage into the active vocabulary and vice versa – when a given foreign word is not actively used, it returns to the passive vocabulary. The dynamics of learning the foreign language determines the result. Knowledge of this dynamic is important for the correct construction of teaching methods and conducting the process of learning a foreign language.

Keywords: Passive Vocabulary; Memorization; Repetition; Language Dynamics; Contextual Memory; Foreign Language Acquisition.

1. Dynamics of Passive and Active Vocabulary in Foreign Language Acquisition

It is natural for foreign language learners to understand some words during conversation or reading, but when it comes time to speak or write, these words disappear. This phenomenon is known as passive and active vocabulary and is crucial for foreign language learning. Our ability to differentiate between these types of vocabulary is very important for anyone trying to acquire or improve their foreign language proficiency.

Passive and active foreign language vocabulary, as well as the dynamics between them, are essential elements of foreign language learning and acquisition. There are two main factors that determine the outcome of foreign language acquisition. On the one hand, these are the motivation and attention of the learner, and on the other hand, an important factor is the process of forgetting. Learning the vocabulary and grammar of a foreign language is a prolonged process that goes through several stages concerning each lexical or grammatical unit.

Each foreign word must first be perceived aurally or read, after which its meaning must be understood. Memorizing foreign words and their active use takes time, during which the studied vocabulary is reviewed repeatedly. The very act of memorizing vocabulary is conditional and variable. In human memory, there are two main sectors where foreign language information is stored: short-term and long-term memory. Information stored in short-term memory needs to be further developed, and information stored in long-term memory must be maintained to avoid being lost.

Knowing foreign vocabulary is a broader concept that includes foreign words whose meanings can be understood only in context, but a word read or heard outside of context can also be understood. On the other hand, there are foreign words that are only understood

but not actively used in speaking or writing. In this regard, the main characteristic of foreign language acquisition can be noted as its dynamic nature.

One of the key tasks in foreign language acquisition is converting passive vocabulary into active vocabulary. This requires constant practice and use of new words in various contexts. Regular review and practice help reinforce vocabulary and prevent forgetting. Additionally, using different learning methods such as listening, reading, writing, and speaking is essential for effective foreign language acquisition.

In conclusion, the dynamics between passive and active vocabulary are crucial for successful foreign language acquisition. Understanding these processes and using appropriate learning methods can significantly improve language skills and facilitate the transition from passive knowledge to active use of the foreign language.

2. Analysis of Passive and Active Foreign Language Vocabulary**2.1. Passive Vocabulary**

Laufer, B., (1998). The passive vocabulary includes words that we recognize and understand when we hear or read them but do not use actively. These can be words encountered in books, movies, or conversations but not fully integrated into our own language use. The passive vocabulary is divided into two categories. In the first category are words that are understood only in context, without being understood out of context. This part of memory is called Contextual Passive Memory. The second category includes words that are understood out of context but not used actively, meaning their level of familiarity is higher than words that can only be understood in context. This part of memory is called Non-contextual Passive Memory. [1]

The passive vocabulary is divided into two categories:

- **Contextual Passive Memory:**
 - Words and expressions understood only within a specific context.
 - Maintained through passive repetition (listening and reading).
- **Non-contextual Passive Memory:**
 - Words and expressions understood even outside a specific context.
 - Maintained through active repetition (active learning, translation).
- **Characteristics of Passive Vocabulary:**
 - Recognition: Words are recognized when seen or heard.
 - Limited Use: Rarely used in active speech or writing.
 - Activation: May require effort to recall and use effectively.

Primary Conclusion:

Passive memory is divided into two categories:

- Contextual Passive Memory: Words and expressions understood only in context, maintained through passive repetition (listening and reading).
- Non-contextual Passive Memory: Words and expressions understood outside context, maintained through active repetition (active learning, translation).

2.2.Active Vocabulary

Laufer, B., (1998). The active vocabulary consists of foreign language words that are frequently and confidently used in daily communication. These are the words that come naturally, without us having to think, when we speak or write. The active vocabulary is a fundamental tool for any foreign language; it is always available and ready for use without the need for a dictionary or reference.

Active vocabulary is a measure of language proficiency and overall fluency. It is dynamic and ever-

changing. Words and expressions that are not used frequently decrease in their level of familiarity within the foreign language vocabulary of the speaker, resulting in their return to one of the previous levels of mastery found in the passive vocabulary. This process of words shifting between active and passive memory highlights the importance of regular usage for maintaining language skills. [1]

• **Characteristics of Active Vocabulary:**

- Frequent Use: Regularly employed in both spoken and written communication.
- Confident and Accurate Use: Words are understood and used correctly, with a high level of confidence.
- Quick and Automatic Recall: Words come to mind effortlessly, without the need for pauses or deep thinking.
- Spontaneity: Ability to use words naturally and spontaneously in various contexts.

Primary Conclusion:

Laufer, B., (1998). Active memory is created after the assimilation of words and expressions. These words are easily accessible and can be used spontaneously and effectively. The dynamic nature of active vocabulary underscores the need for consistent practice and engagement with the language to ensure that words remain readily available for use. Regular interaction with the language, through speaking, writing, and other forms of communication, is essential for maintaining and expanding one's active vocabulary.

3. Analysis of Kostadinov's Model of Passive and Active Foreign Language Vocabulary Dynamics

Ognyan Kostadinov's model for the dynamics of passive and active foreign language vocabulary is presented in a table that examines the different stages and processes related to the acquisition and use of foreign words (Table 1).

Table 1

KOSTADINOV'S MODEL OF PASSIVE AND ACTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY DYNAMICS							
LISTENING		PASSIVE		ACTIVE		ACTIVATION	SPEAKING
RECEPTION	INTERPRETATION	CONTEXTUAL PASSIVE MEMORY	NON-CONTEXTUAL PASSIVE MEMORY	ASSIMILATION	DYNAMICS	← →	ACTIVE
FOREIGN WORDS	COMPREHENSION TRANSLATION						MEMORY
READING		REPETITION	REPETITION	PRACTICE	FADING		WRITING

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The analysis of this model can be described as follows:

- **Reception of Foreign Words (INPUT Info):**
 - Listening and Reading are the primary methods for receiving new information. These activities include:
 - **Understanding of meaning by:**
 - Interpretation: Understanding the meaning of words in the context of the sentence.
 - Comprehension: Fully grasping the meaning of the text.
 - Translation: Translating words or text into the native language.

- **Passive Memory:**
 - This stage includes ****Memorization**** and ****Contextual Passive Memory****. Words are memorized in the context in which they are encountered, aiding better retention.
- **Active Memory:**
 - Non-Contextual Passive Memory^{**}: Words are memorized without connection to a specific context.
 - Repetition: Repeating words helps retain them longer and transition them to active memory.
- **Active Usage:**
 - Assimilation: Integrating new words into active vocabulary through **Practice** and **Activation**, leading to dynamic use in speech and writing.

– Dynamics: Transition of words between active and passive memory depending on frequency of use.

- **Speaking and Writing (OUTPUT Info):**

– These activities represent the ultimate goals of the model—the active use of foreign words in speech and written texts.

This model emphasizes the importance of both passive and active learning strategies, highlighting the dynamic nature of vocabulary acquisition and retention. It illustrates the process from passive to active memory through practical application and repetition, underscoring the necessity of frequent use for maintaining an active vocabulary.

- **Key points of the model include:**

– The importance of practice and repetition for retention and activation of foreign words.

– The significance of context for effective memorization and understanding.

– The process of fading, where infrequent use leads to words transitioning from active to passive memory.

4. Basic Stages of Foreign Word Acquisition and Knowledge Transition from Passive to Active Vocabulary

Via listening to, reading, and writing texts, as well as via the use of visual dictionaries that offer each word in textual form together with a picture, we can acquaint with foreign vocabulary. The use of word cards and the repetition of reading phrases from dictionaries are also standard practices. It is also beneficial to make use of all the available ways to learn foreign words, as this will ensure effective and long-lasting memory. One of the most important factors in keeping new language is consistent exposure and practice. In addition, participating in discussions and using language that is applicable to real-world situations strengthens both memory and comprehension.

4.1. Listening to Unfamiliar Words:

The first stage is to get comfortable with foreign words by listening to them several times without being aware of what they signify in one's home language. The listener is supposed to adjust their ears to the sounds to achieve the aim. Hearing a foreign word several times helps in its memory, which in turn causes the listener to view the word as being familiar each time they hear it. The first step in being comfortable with a foreign term is to get familiar with it. This stage assists the student in becoming used to the phonetic structure of the new language he or she is learning.

4.2. Using Expressions with Unfamiliar Words:

When there are phrases that include words that are not easily understood in a foreign language, it is important to learn them in the appropriate manner. For students who are learning a foreign language, it is of utmost importance to comprehend the meaning of new

terms in the context in which they are used. However, the degree of difficulty of these expressions must correspond with the amount of knowledge that they possess; otherwise, relying on a dictionary, which may be distracting, is not the most effective method. New words are easier to recall when they are associated with previously learned ideas, which is accomplished via contextual learning.

4.3. Repetition of Foreign Words and Building Passive Vocabulary:

Passive vocabulary consists of two distinct categories: contextual and non-contextual words. These represent separate groups within the realm of passive vocabulary. The transition of words from contextual to non-contextual occurs through continuous exposure to a variety of texts, whether through listening or reading. This process exemplifies a dynamic interaction within passive vocabulary, where the acquisition and assimilation of words undergo transformative phases.

4.4. Utilizing Dictionaries and Digital Tools for Vocabulary Enhancement:

In the later stages of learning, students should employ dictionaries to delve into unfamiliar words, comprehending their fundamental meanings and broader applications. Additionally, numerous digital dictionaries offer audio features, enabling users to listen to the pronunciation of the word. Moreover, these dictionaries often provide contextual sentence examples, significantly aiding in grasping the accurate meaning of the word and facilitating its retention. This phase represents the mastery stage in enhancing one's familiarity with words. By utilizing sentence examples, learners can better grasp the proper usage and nuances of the word.

4.5. Mastering Memory: The Art of Effective Retention and Repetition

Memorization is not a single act, and to memorize information effectively, it is important to repeat what we have learned a great number of times.

Marousis, A., (2023). According to Harman Ebbinghaus's forgetting curve, the retention rate of information decreases over time:

– After 1 hour about 50% of the information is retained.

– After 1 day about 30% of the information is retained.

– After 1 week about 10% of the information is retained.[2]

Jaap, M., Murre, J., Dros, J. (2015). These values are approximate and may vary depending on various factors such as methods and individual differences. The Ebbinghaus Forgetting Curve (fig. 1) shows how quickly new information can be retained if it is not used or practiced regularly.

Figure 1

The repetitions should be planned out and spaced out over a period of one month to assist the learner's passive memory in absorbing the knowledge. To boost retention, this strategy makes use of the spacing effect, which involves extending the amount of time that passes between review sessions. Reviewing the content on a regular basis helps to reinforce the knowledge, which in turn increases the probability that it will be retained in long-term memory.

According to Harman Ebbinghaus, the forgetting curve (fig. 2) with periodic negotiation of what has

been learned every 12 hours illustrates how regular repetition of information significantly improves its retention in memory:

- 1 hour after learning about 50% of the information is retained.
- 12 hours after the first repetition the retention increases to 70%.
- 24 hours after learning (after the second repetition) retention is around 60%.
- After each subsequent iteration, the retention rate increases or stabilizes at high levels.

Figure 2

Regular repetition helps consolidate knowledge in long-term memory and significantly minimizes the pace at which information is forgotten. This may be accomplished using the most efficient means possible, which include the comprehension of relevant educational information by reading and comprehension. One example of this would be viewing films or television shows that are captivating and that pique the learner's interest and curiosity. It is possible that we may refer to this task as the third stage of learning foreign words since it is a job that will never be finished. Within the context of building passive vocabulary in a foreign language, this stage acts as a transitional stage leading to the fourth step. [3]

4.6. Transition from Passive to Active Memory:

Passive memory is often where a foreign word is stored after it has been mastered. When the words are spoken or heard often, they have the potential to enter active memory. As a rule, we need to take into consideration the fact that passive foreign language study, which includes listening to comprehension and reading comprehension, often only results in the improvement of passive memory. Only a small number of passive words can make their way into active memory without conscious effort. It is necessary to participate in active use, such as speaking or writing, to develop one's active vocabulary. This is because active usage helps to reinforce the words that are learnt via practical application. This is the fourth step of creating an active vocabulary inside a foreign language, often known as the process

of acquiring foreign words. Active use of the foreign language, which involves conversation as well as verbal and written translation from the native language into the foreign language, is the most effective method for accomplishing this goal.

4.7. Building Active Vocabulary:

Active foreign language vocabulary building is the last stage of memorization. It necessitates the active use of foreign words. This could be accomplished through dialog, oral, or written translations from a native language into a foreign language. The active foreign language vocabulary is based on passive vocabulary. Only after repeated use of passive words and their active use in speaking and writing can we expect to enhance active vocabulary. Practical usage solidifies the transition of words from passive to active memory. The level of fluency and proficiency in a foreign language measures the permanent process of building an active vocabulary.

Active vocabulary building is the final stage of memorization for acquiring foreign words. It requires actively using these words in various contexts. Dialogue, oral practice, or written translations from one's native language into the foreign language can achieve this active utilization of foreign words. A language builds its active vocabulary on its passive vocabulary. Mastery of words, initially encountered passively, only comes after repeated use in speaking and writing. Practical application further solidifies the transition of words from passive to active memory, reinforcing language acquisition. "The development of active vocabulary is an ongoing process in foreign language acquisition, measured by one's fluency and proficiency in the language.

4.8. Maintaining Vocabulary:

There is a possibility that some words may return to their passive form if we do not make consistent use

of them in our active vocabulary. When it comes to keeping an active vocabulary, regular practice and use are very necessary. It is helpful to keep words active and prevent them from reverting to passive memory by reviewing them and utilizing them in a variety of settings. Active and passive language usage on a regular basis may assist in the maintenance of vocabulary in a foreign language.

Conclusion:

The study outlines a model of passive and active foreign language vocabulary dynamics, emphasizing the importance of memorization and forgetting in language learning. It differentiates between passive vocabulary (words recognized and understood but not actively used) and active vocabulary (words frequently and confidently used in daily communication). The dynamic nature of vocabulary acquisition involves a continuous movement of words between passive and active states. Regular practice and repetition are crucial for maintaining and expanding active vocabulary. Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing effective teaching methods and enhancing language learning outcomes.

References

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